

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PROSTATE BIOPSY AND OTHER METHODS OF PROSTATE EXAMINATION IN EARLY DETECTION OF PROSTATE CANCER

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Abstract

One of the main tasks of modern urology is the early diagnosis of prostate cancer (PC) and the search for more effective methods of its treatment. It is important to distinguish an oncological tumor from hyperplasia and other neoplasms in time.[1]

Prostate cancer (PC) is the most common malignancy of the urogenital system in men. Prostate cancer is rarely diagnosed in men under the age of 40, with most cases occurring in men aged 50-70.

An important indicator of the informativeness of diagnostic methods depends on the number of really positive results, among other tests and sensitivity.[8]

A complex of studies is always required to make a diagnosis.

Keywords

Benign prostatic hyperplasia, Body mass index, Prostate gland, Prostate cancer, Digital Rectal Examination, Transrectal ultrasound, Prostate specific antigen, Prostate Index, Ultrasound diagnostics, Transrectal ultrasound, Radical prostatectomy[4]

Problem

Men do not always go to the urologist after the age of 50, and in some cases, the results of the initial prostate examination methods are not continued even after the subsequent examinations. As a result, in most cases, prostate cancer is detected in patients during the development of the disease and metastasis. This reduces the positive aspects of the treatment process and increases the risk of death.

The goal.

The purpose of the study was to select the most optimal methods that help in early, accurate diagnosis of prostate cancer and early prevention of complications, and to compare their advantages and disadvantages with each other. To do this, make statistics by comparing the selected test results with each other.[10]

Improving the diagnosis of prostate cancer by optimizing the prostate biopsy scheme and creating an algorithm for its implementation.

To achieve this goal, we set the following three tasks for the study:

1. Evaluation of the value of prostate biopsy results in prostate gland examinations.

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2. Evaluation of the impact of prostate gland examinations other than biopsy on the probability of detecting prostate cancer.
3. Development of an optimal individual algorithm for prostate biopsy.

The result.

To achieve this goal, 82 patients with prostate problems were selected and studied retrospectively. Their age ranged from 48 to 89 years. RSCU has been selected as the location for the research. Patients from 05.09.2020 to 10.03. Selected for scientific work until 2023.

We conducted standard tests used in the diagnosis of PC in our urology center. These tests are DRE, Ultrasound, TRUS, PSA, MRI and Prostate Biopsy.

Biopsy of PB (Prostate Gland) - In this examination, a biopsy examination was performed in patients, and differential diagnosis of BPH and PC was made.

A prostate biopsy is a very minor procedure that can be done in a hospital. Local anesthetics are often used for pain relief, and in this case the procedure is performed on an outpatient basis. If general anesthesia, spinal or epidural anesthesia is required, it is also performed after hospitalization in the hospital, inpatient hospitalization, where it is up to two days after the operation.

During the examination, we noted the following parameters: PG (Prostate Gland) Biopsy - In this examination, a biopsy examination was performed in patients, and differential diagnosis of PBXG and PC was made. We examined 82 patients with TRUS

- Prostate gland (PB) size;
- Symmetry of two pieces;
- Structure of PB boundaries;
- Whether there are knots or not;
- Hardening (calcification) or not.

We will analyze the results.

The accuracy rate in diagnosing PC by DRE is only 10.97%. But the probability of getting PC from suspected patients is equal to 81.81%. Therefore, we cannot say that patients without suspicion of PC are healthy or PC-free by DRE results, and we should conduct other examinations after DRE.

The accuracy level in diagnosing PC by US is only 2.4%. But the probability of getting PC from suspected patients is 100%. Therefore, we cannot say that patients without suspicion of PC are healthy or PC-free by US results, and we need to conduct other examinations after US.

The level of accuracy in diagnosing PC by TRUS is only 12.19%. But the probability of getting PC from suspected patients is 91%. Therefore, we cannot say that patients without suspicion of PC are healthy or PC-free by TRUS results, and we need to conduct other examinations after TRUS.

The level of accuracy in diagnosing PC by PSA is only 45.12%. But the probability of getting PC from suspected patients is equal to 53.7%. Therefore, we cannot say that patients without PC suspicion are healthy or PC-free by PSA results, and we should conduct other tests after PSA.

The accuracy of MRI results in PC diagnosis is 64.7%. It certainly helps to diagnose the disease with almost higher accuracy. But this examination mainly determines the advanced stage of the disease,

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i.e. the stage of metastasis. But if the biopsy is performed based on the results of the MRI, the accuracy of the examination will increase.

CONCLUSION.

1. Based on the results of our scientific work, PB biopsy has a very important and decisive place in PC. Because through this examination, the final diagnosis of PC can be determined according to the exact level and stages. The rest of the examinations are considered auxiliary methods for the accurate diagnosis of PC in patients.
2. Pre-biopsy examinations in the diagnosis of PC make it possible to select from a large population of patients even patients with a small amount of suspected PC. Screening patients once every 6 months or 1 year to determine whether there is suspicion of PC or not.
3. The results of our investigations showed that PC disease can occur in men aged 48 to 90 years. The age limit is too big. Therefore, taking into account that the limit of this disease is increasing and the number of encounters is increasing, it is necessary to develop an algorithm for the prevention of this disease.

Practical recommendations.

In the first place, promotion of PC disease among the population. To explain this disease to young people (men). Checking them after the age of 45. Minimize production factors as much as possible.

At the next stage, non-invasive way, i.e. organizing PB US and PSA tests at least every year. If a change in US examinations and PSA analysis or complaints of prostatitis increase in the patient, use of DRI examinations.

After that, a TRUS examination must be conducted. If the results of at least 2 examinations are + in the summary of the above examinations, then the patient should be sent for a CT examination.

The last decisive step is the conclusion of the above examinations, which of the results of DRI, TRUS and CT is positive. A PB biopsy is recommended.

References.

1. Klinicheskie rekomendatsii rak predstatelnoy zhelezy "Odobreno na zesedanii nauchno-prakticheskogo soveta Ministerstva zdrovokhraneniya Rossiyskoy Federatsii (protocol ot 22.11.2019g. No. 08/2-3-4)"
2. Stanford JL, Stephenson RA, Coyle LM. et al. Prostate Cancer Trends 1973–1995. SEER Program, National Cancer Institute, NIH Pub.; 99–4543, Bethesda: MD; 1999.
3. Steinberg G.D., Carter B.S., Beaty T.H. et al. Family history and the risk of prostate cancer. Prostate 1990;17:337–437.
4. Stewart R.W. et al. Screening for prostate cancer. Semin Oncol 2017;44:47.
5. Prakticheskie rekomendatsii RUSSCO #3s2, 2022 (volume 12). 607–626.
6. Collective authors: Nosov D.A., Volkova M.I., Gladkov O.A., Karabina E.V., Krylov V.V., Matveev V.B., Mitin T., Popov A.M. . <https://rosoncoweb.ru/standarts/RUSSCO/2022/2022-31.pdf>

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konferensiya

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7. Sostoyanie onkologicheskoy pomoshchi naseleniyu Rossii v 2018 godu. Pod ed. A.D. Kaprina, V.V. Starinsky, G.V. Petrov. M.; 2019.
8. Lee F., ThorpPedersen ST, Siders DB. et al. Transrectal ultrasound in the diagnosis and staging of prostate cancer. Radiology 1989;170:609–615.
9. Wang R. et al. Prebiopsy mp-MRI Can Help to Improve the Predictive Performance in Prostate Cancer: A Prospective Study in 1,478 Consecutive Patients. Clin Cancer Res 2017;23:3692.
10. Volobuev A.I., Ivanova L.A., Kulabukhova E.A. Rukovodstvo po luchevoj diagnostics and gynecology. SPb.: ELBI-SPb, 2008. [Vobo`lakuyev A.I., Ivanova L.A., Kulabukhova E.A. Guidelines for diagnostic radiology in gynecology. Saint Petersburg: ELBI-SPb, 2008. (In Russ.)].
11. Fuchsjager M., Akin O., Shukla-Dave A. et al. The role of MRI and MRSI in diagnosis, treatment selection, and post-treatment follow-up for prostate cancer. Cin Adv Hematol Oncol 2009;7(3):193–202.
12. Mishchenko A.V., Dubitsky D.L., Moskalenko E.A. Vozmojnosti magnetic-resonance spectroscopy and diagnosis of adenocarcinoma predstatelnoy signs. Luchevaya diagnosis and therapy 2010;4(1):62–7. [Mischenko A.V., Dubitsky D.L., Moskalenko E.A. Value of magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging in the diagnosis of prostate cancer. Diagnostic and therapeutic radiology 2010;4(1):62–7. (In Russ.)].
13. Mullerad M., Castin A., Adusumilli P.S. et al. Comparison of nephron-sparing surgery in central versus peripheral renal tumors. Urology 2005;65(3):467–72.
14. D'Amico A.V., Whittington R., Schnall M. et al. The impact of the inclusion of endorectal coil magnetic resonance imaging in a multivariate analysis to predict clinically unsuspected extraprostatic cancer. Cancer 1995;75(9):2368–72.
15. Jager G.J., Ruijter E.T., van de Kaa C.A. et al. Local staging of prostate cancer with endorectal MR imaging: correlation with histopathology. AJR 1996;166(4):845–52.